

DIFFERENCE ANALYSIS OF MAIN TYPES OF SECURITIES

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First next, this proprietary obligations perform the right is the company of benefit one part to get, to borrow received money return and etc. From this except, the company in the activity - for example, shareholders at the meeting participation reach to the right have to be too can Precious the paper present reach through action the owner own rights done to increase possible (for example, dividends get, meeting sound give) or them sell through another to the individual to pass can

Precious papers one how many to criteria according to classified. Most the main thing this the following is the division :

Shareable valuable papers. To these **simple or preferential shares** enters Shareable valuable papers company and his dividends in the form of in favor of to share has been the right confirms. From this except, such valuable papers the company in management sound to give the right gives, but this right of share to the size depends will be That is, share how much big if, action of the owner effect so much strong will be Precious of papers control package said concept exists, that is to the company about main decisions acceptance to do for enough in quantity shares ;

Debt valuable papers - **bonds**. They are of the owner debt known from the deadline after demand to do and to him percentages to be paid the right confirms. Indeed, debt valuable paper buy take, the owner own funds to the company into debt gives and company own in turn this money back to give and regularly respectively interest (coupons or discount) to pay obligation takes

Precious to papers investment input through the investor own from investment benefit to receive waits Precious from papers removable income two different to be can :

- of the asset himself take coming income From these actions removable dividends from bonds while coupons to be possible ;
- speculative, that is valuable the paper buy get and sell price between difference because of received income

Calculated of income main types this dividends and are coupons. Dividends are company of benefit one part to shareholders to pay Dividends to pay periodicity and volume one row to factors, that's it including of the company to success depend That's

why for, shares buy while receiving bonds from coupons different as, this income source that it is not guaranteed to know need From the bond received income bond term until it's over until company to you to pay which guarantees credit according to percentages is like

Speculative income in the market in advance telling which cannot be income is considered Value increase possible has been promising valuable papers to determine one how many the way there is. Speculative investment strategy action did investors shares cheap in price buy to get and maximum difference with they are own of the price the most high to the top when it comes out to sell movement they do However, in the market shares of value to increase never who guarantee give can't.

Actions from bonds how difference does : comparison schedule

characteristics / parameters	Action	Bond
Precious paper type	Shareable	Debt
Issuer	" Shareholding society " organizational to the shape have has been companies	State, municipalities, each how management to the shape have companies
Benefit get conditions	Not guaranteed, not specified	Guaranteed, specified to the amount have to be possible
Potentially benefit	Tall	Low
Ownership to do term	Not limited	Term there is
Risk level	Higher	Lower
Rights and powers	Precious papers the owner society in business participation reach possible and his property have to be to the right have	Property and in management participation reach the right no

this question clearly and simple answer no In general all of them two to the factor depends on:

- pending profit
- acceptance to be done risk level

Here again one parameter to add can : investor transactions done increase for to spend ready has been time If for the investor guaranteed constant passive income get important if, it is defined coupon payments with high liquid bonds preferred to see can Such valuable papers according to benefit state or big corporations by guaranteed.

However, high reliability and minimal participation in the process reach In return, the investor receives a relatively low return takes, rarely cases from 10-12% per year increases.

Capital investment of doing dangerous methods inclined those who are for shares more suitable will come Risks much high, but income bonds with cannot be compared. That's why for all investment decisions attention with analysis to be done need This is the process significant level the time to spend demand does, of the investor valuable papers market principles according to knowledge have to be need about while not to speak.

Simple by doing in other words, shares and to bonds investment of strategies main the difference that is, shares big risk taking with high income to get directed, bonds while safer and in advance forecast to be done, however less amount income to get directed.

To actions investment to do strategy the first in line acceptance done risk taking account received without possible has been maximum benefit to get directed if, bonds owners and low level risk, state guarantees of the issuer reliability and others in return much less income to receive preferred they see

Companies shares, bonds and their quotes according to in detail information Investments on the page get can

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